

Assessment Submission Form

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Declaration of Authorship

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Signed *Kantowska* Date 05.07.2024

POCEA

Sustainable revolution in menstrual care

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to conduct research regarding the development of a new innovative product Pocea that is a sustainable alternative to conventional feminine menstrual pads. Furthermore, this research will examine the significant impact feminine hygiene products have on the environment and therefore human health. Additionally, we wish to discuss the issue of low menstrual education and the taboo surrounding menstruation in undeveloped and developing countries.

Our findings suggest that our product Pocea can be beneficial in both developed and undeveloped countries.

Pocea is produced using only reusable and fully decomposable materials, making it environmental friendly. It can be reused up to 2 times. It is also easy to manufacture with only basic equipment.

Finally, it fulfills the 9 out of 17 United Nations goals:

- No Poverty
- Good Health and Well-Being
- Quality Education
- Gender Equality
- Clean water and Sanitation
- Responsible consumption, and production.
- Climate Action
- Life below Water
- Life on Land

KEYWORDS

Female Hygiene Products (FHPs), FHP's disposal, Environmental implications, Sustainability, Reusable, Cost effective, Period poverty, Menstruation taboo

INTRODUCTION

(Zuzanna) Menstruation is a bodily and healthy process controlled by hormones. Bleeding associated with it is caused by shedding of the endometrium. 1.8 billion people menstruate worldwide in a month, comprising 26% of the global population. On a given day, 800 million women and girls menstruate. Over that period of time, hygiene products such as sanitary pad, menstrual cups and tampons are used to absorb the discharge and keep the user feeling clean and comfortable throughout the day.

Among these products sanitary pads are the most commonly used, however we believe that they have many disadvantages.

There are two main motivations that are also the objectives behind the idea of developing Pocea – sustainable alternative to conventional feminine menstrual pads:

1. **ENVIRONMENT:** Environmental concern caused by significant waste production.
2. **ACCESSIBILITY AND TABOO:** Low accessibility of feminine hygiene products in undeveloped and developing countries along with the taboo surrounding menstruation.

Pocea aims to address both issues and be a product that is eco-friendly, accessible and easy to manufacture.

1. ENVIRONMENT

There is no doubt that climate change remains a huge threat to society. In the past years, we have observed rising temperatures, higher frequencies of natural disasters, rising sea levels, water and land pollution, and chemical contaminations. These have caused communities and individuals around the world to suffer mentally, physically and financially.

It is certain that many factors contribute towards climate change. Yet the biggest one is land pollution (Bell et.al, 2024).

FHPs disposal is responsible for huge amounts of non-recyclable waste worldwide. Over the course of a lifetime, on average, a single user will use approximately 10,000 pads. These later, are thrown out as solid waste and end up in landfills, where they are estimated to take 500 to 800 years to break down. But truly, materials such as plastic never biodegrade completely. During decomposition, the plastics break down into microplastics, which have now, even found their way into humans and other animals. Additionally, the carbon footprint of such products is very high, with annual usage leaving 5.3 kg CO₂ equivalents per person.

That is why we were looking for substitutes for pads that are made from plastic and single used. Pocea uses corn husk (that is considered a farm waste), cotton and beeswax. All of the components of the pad are cheap, easily accessible, biodegradable and safe for use in contact with skin. Additionally, the pad production is not complicated and does not require special equipment.

2. ACCESSIBILITY AND TABOO

Menstruation's impact on the environment is an issue of great importance. Despite that, many specialists call for immediate action this matter is not discussed enough as it still remains a taboo topic.

Even though, currently there are products that are supposed to be less harmful to the environment. (Such as menstrual cups, multiple use pads, etc.), there still remains the issue of low accessibility and awareness about them, especially in less developed countries. In which menstruation still remains something that women are ashamed of and where education about period is not sufficient and where the awareness about environment and ecology is poorer.

That is why with Pocea we wish to fight for women's comfort around the world. Menstruation should not be a reason to be ashamed, be isolated from social life and school or be considered unclean.

Another aspect of poor menstruation hygiene is the high risk of urinary and reproductive tract infections. Since some women in undeveloped and developing countries do not have access to sanitary products, they use materials such as rags to absorb the discharge. These are usually not cleaned and sanitized properly due to a lack of clean water. Poor hygiene makes women more susceptible to numerous additional illnesses. Therefore the risk of infections and possible complications are very high. And, these can cause irreversible damage to women's bodies, including infertility.

The concerns cumulate into the concept of "Period Poverty", it is described as "the lack of access to menstrual hygiene products, water, soap, and private safe clean sanitation services to manage menstrual cycles". This is the particular term now used to describe this condition.

Of course these two issues coexist. Undeveloped countries usually are less educated about the environment and because of the taboo surrounding periods they do not discuss it and take no action towards becoming more sustainable.

(Enosh) Why the name Pocea?

The name Pocea was inspired around the scientific term of "Poaceae", a subclass of the order "Poales" is the grass family of "Monocotyledonous" flowering plants. The Poaceae family is considered to be the primary food sources in the world, in terms of species count, they are ranked among the top five families of flowering plants of the Earth's flora (Campbell, 2020). Our product is encircling on this certain species of grass family; and that is "**corn**" a member of the poaceae family in which we utilize the husk of the corn, which will be discussed on this research on how it would be harnessed.

METHODOLOGY

The structure of this research paper has been divided into two main parts. Methodology and research approach is different for both of them.

Part I – Deductive research

This part focuses on environmental analysis along with discussing the accessibility of FHP products and taboo surrounding menstruation. This part uses only secondary data sourced from articles, reports, and researches. We have reviewed them critically and drew conclusions presented in the Literature review with research background.

Part II – Inductive research

This part includes results of a lab research conducted on the components of Pocea pads. The tests took place in a lab in Kuwait at Aspire Indian International School along with the guidance of Varsha Arunkumar a teacher in the same respected school and provided primary data needed to examine the properties of the absorbent material made from corn husk.

Null Hypothesis:

Corn husk fibres cannot be used as an efficient absorbent in making Pocea Eco Pads and will not be a cost-effective solution.

PART 1
**LITERATURE REVIEW
AND
RESEARCH BACKGROUND**

General climate change

(Enosh) Over 15% of methane emissions is caused by the disposal of single-use plastics in landfills. Both the size of the landfill and these emissions rise when more plastics are disposed of in them. (Vasarhelyi, 2023)

According to the European Commission, menstruation products are among the most frequently found single use plastic items in the marine environment, ranking fifth overall. Plastic never really biodegrades, which are estimated to take 500-800 years to decompose in landfills. Furthermore, it is evident that some tampons come with plastic applicators in addition to having plastic in their core, approximately 90% of standard “single-use” sanitary pads are made of plastic. The amount of period products in the marine life and the oceans it considered to be a big concern in today’s world. The numerous number of pads and tampons that are reportedly disposed of in landfills annually exceeds making it around 20 billion, and it could take hundreds of years to degrade.

This remains a huge concern as it is caused by more than solely one factor. Greenhouse gasses, chemical pollution, but the main factor is land pollution. A big chunk of land pollution is caused by production and disposal of FHPs. We recognized that the climate change and extreme heat caused by it is a rising threat to the society. As global warming remains a huge concern, a lot of researches have been conducted regarding HPS disposal and its impact on the environment.

How much waste is produced every year?

An average woman menstruates for time equivalent to 3,000 days, which is almost 8.2 years, during her lifetime. In that duration, a female will typically utilize 12,000 pads on average which is well around 150 kilograms per individual making it sufficient to fill two minibuses. Each menstrual component as mentioned before consists of 90% plastic on average. In other words, the equivalent of four plastic bags can be found in a “single conventional pack of menstruation pads”.

Several polices and standards are being implemented for various products under the EU’s “Directive on single-use plastics”. In consideration of inclusion whether there are more sustainable options, these measures are designed to correspondent and produce the best outcomes.

The directive focuses on the following ten issues or items:
(European Commission, 2019)

- “Cotton bud sticks”
- “Cutlery, plates, straws and stirrers”
- “Balloons and sticks for balloons”
- “Food containers”
- “Cups for beverages”
- “Cigarette butts”
- “Plastic bags”
- “Packets and wrappers”
- **“Wet wipes and sanitary items”**

As per the law the plastic products that are designed to be single-use often are prohibited from being sold in EU member states.

As EU claims that single use plastic is a major issue. So is the 12 billion disposal menstrual products that are annually disposed. This explains how the environment is polluted. Talking about sanitary pads which are usually single used and tend to contain well up to 90% of plastic. “ 49 billion and 19 billion single-use menstrual product are consumed each year in the EU and USA” (Recommendations from Life Cycle Assessments Single-use menstrual products and their alternatives hosted by, n.d.)

Issues faced due to decomposing plastic and how microplastic along with its chemicals can impact on human health

There is a serious environmental risk associated with using sanitary pads because they take a quite considerable amount to break down. Each sanitary napkin generates 2g of non-biodegradable plastic residue. The management of menstrual hygiene (MHM) may become unhygienic due to a lack of suitable and secure disposal methods (MSA Hameed, 2024). Burning napkins has the potential to produce dioxin, which can lead to pollution and other detrimental effects on the environment (Borooah, Chanakya and Dasappa, 2020).

One of the most haunting questions is if using single-use plastic sanitary napkins can cause cancer? One of the causes of cancer in women can be the substance phthalate which is used to soften and enhance the pliability and durability of plastics. Some studies show that having a connected prolonged exposure to these substances, which are known as “endocrine disruptors” can become apart of the reason to obesity, asthma, reduced fertility and breast cancer. (Can sanitary pads cause cancer? Here’s what experts say, 2022).

Nonetheless, using tampons and other sanitary products that contain most plastic or that are meant to be single use have raised significant concerns regarding the possible dioxin

exposure. According to the definition published by the (WHO, 2016) “Dioxins is a highly toxic and can cause reproductive and developmental problems, damage the immune system, interfere with hormones and cause cancer”. Even though the comprehensive role of sanitary pads is to be safe to use, the concern of over exposure to dioxins remains a hazard. The correlation between the incidence of genital cancer is due to the absorption of substances like dioxin and of “super-absorbent polymer has been the subject of numerous ongoing studies. Cervical and ovarian cancers may arise from dioxin accumulation within the body and can possibly impact women’s reproductive systems. In essence, it is a carcinogen meaning that it promotes the growth of cells in your body that causes cancer. (Ghadyalpatil, n.d.)

Certain artificially scented pads which are fragranced and dyed to mask odors and enhance their aesthetic appeal can also be harmful as they contain chemicals frequently aggravating pre-existing sensitivities and cause allergic reactions. That can irritate the skin, cause hives or swelling and itching. Additionally, it can trigger allergic reaction, or affect the intimate area’s pH balance.

Rising challenges between developed and developing or underdeveloped countries.
What is meant by the term “Period Poverty”?

According to the definition that was put up by the UN Women (2024) it states that “Period poverty” refers to the inability to afford and access menstrual products, sanitation and hygiene facilities and education and awareness to manage menstrual health. Period Poverty is something which is faced in every country around the world, from the developed to the underdeveloped, no matter rich or poor is it indeed a global health issue.

For instance, teenage girls and women that reside in the urban areas tend to use sanitary pads more presumably than those who live in the rural areas. They are almost forced to use “cloth” due to inaccessibility of proper FHPs, in Zimbabwe, Bangladesh, Egypt, India, Madagascar and many more. (WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Program for water supply, sanitation and hygiene, n.d.)

Now putting this into perspective of the “United States of America” (USA), particularly among the teens of colors and those from the lower-class household. One in four teenagers and one in three adults in the US struggle to afford any sort of menstrual sanitary products. (Period.org, n.d.). Same issues have been observed as well as in Canada:

“Three in ten Canadian adults who menstruate say they or their family have struggled to afford menstrual products” (Period.org, n.d.)

Meanwhile, another research claims that, in response to a recent survey on the experiences of the girls in the UK (conducted by “Plan International UK”) revealed that three out of ten girls had difficulties accessing or even unable to afford any sort of menstrual sanitary

wear or products during the lockdown due to the “COVID-19 outbreak”. Additionally, more than half (54%) of them as they had no other choice had turned to toilet paper as a substitute. (Plan International UK, n.d.)

In 2023, 6 months into the Gaza war, women struggle everyday. Over 10 000 of them have reportedly been killed to date, with an estimated 6,000 of them being mothers who abandoned 19 000 children, according to UN Women. The women that were lucky enough to make through the rumble have been left homeless, bereaved and threatened with famine. **In addition to having no access to clean water, restrooms, latrines, “sanitary pads”** due to these circumstances over a million women and girls in Gaza face growing rates in illness due to their appalling living circumstances. Considering this was reported to happen in 2023, in the present days it might have gotten even worse. (UN Women – Headquarters, 2023)

Menstrual pads and other locally produced hygiene products saw an astronomical price increase in Lebanon between “98% and 234%” during the country’s economic downturn. Since menstruation was and still is a taboo subject, most girls and women are afraid to discuss it. Making matters worse more than half, that is “66%” of girls in April 2020, said that they could not afford to purchase menstrual products. (Plan International Lebanon, n.d.)

In Myanmar due to the “high risk of natural hazards” women and girls who are internally displaced, frequently experience lack of private spaces to shower and change, both during travel and in camps. Most of these women and girls are constrained into using cloths as an alternative instead of sanitary pads due to it’s unavailability . (Schmitt et al., 2017)

Taking into consideration all of these circumstances that the community that menstruates undergoes, gave us the ground of coming up with the idea of Pocea eco pads. Our product “Pocea” can make a major change in their lifestyles, it can be a revolution in the menstrual care around the world.

Hence, our motivation to prepare a product that is sustainable, affordable, biodegradable, easy to use and accessible. For these reasons we have started the research development of Pocea eco pads. Part II of this study will cover the lab research.

PART II **LAB RESEARCH AND PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT**

(Zuzanna) Lab research is crucial for developing a new product, especially if it is a hygienic product that will be used directly on skin. Therefore, in the lab we have conducted a series of tests to ensure that the Pocea pad is safe, serves its all function and is easy to manufacture. The last aim was especially important as we wish to provide it to women that do not have access to FHPs on a daily basis.

* Ethics Form has been approved by the Univesrsity's authoreties and
can be found in the end of the of this research paper *

The study can be divided in the following way:

1. Extraction of Husk Fiber.
2. Preparation of the final product.
3. Testing of the prepared product (Including: absorption, tensile strength, flammability and biodegradability).

1. EXTRACTION OF THE HUSK FIBER

Waste plant materials were collected for fiber extraction. Three different plant materials were kept for further tests: corn husk, pineapple leaves, and bamboo leaves (Fig 1).

These were washed and kept in water for 40 days (pineapple, bamboo leaves) and 30 days (corn husk) under sunlight to allow them to rot. This was crucial for helping the breakdown of the fibers. This process is called retting. The water was changed regularly to prevent odor from being produced.

After this period, the leaves were washed again and boiled for a duration of 1 hour and then left to cool (Fig 2, Fig 3, Fig 4, Fig 5). This left us with the fibers from the leaves (Fig 6, Fig 7).

(Fig 1) Collection of fibers and retting

(Fig 2) Boiling and cooling of corn husk fiber

(Fig 3) Cooling of corn husk fiber

(Fig 4) Boiling of pineapple leaves fiber

(Fig 5) Cooling of pineapple leaves fiber

(Fig 6) Absorbent made from corn husk fibers

(Fig 7) Absorbent made from pineapple husk fibers

2. PREPARATION OF THE FINAL PRODUCT

The sanitary napkins consist of four layers (Fig 8):

- Two overlapping layers of cotton cloth,
- Layer of beeswax and cinnamon,
- Layer of plant fiber,
- Two overlapping layers of cotton cloth.

These were then stitched together in the typical size and shape of a disposable sanitary napkin to create the final product – Pocea Eco Pad (Fig 9).

The choice of materials was determined by the following factors: comfort:

- Cotton is widely available, breathable, decomposable, soft and relatively cheap.
- Beeswax and cinnamon layer help with leakage as well as serve an antibacterial purpose.
- Plant fibers were chosen because of their low cost, biodegradability and high absorbency.

This combination ensures absorbency, accessibility and low cost of production.

(Fig 8) Layers of the sanitary pad

(Fig 9) Finished product

3. TESTING THE PREPARED PRODUCT

A series of tests were conducted to ensure that the Pocea pad is safe, absorbs liquid, is not susceptible to tearing, is not flammable, may be decomposed and there is a low risk of leakage.

Testes and their results are as followed:

Absorption test:

The separated fiber was first weighed and then placed in a beaker with 50ml of water. This was left for an hour after which its weight was rechecked. A change in weight would indicate that the fiber had absorbed the liquid (Fig 10).

Results of the absorption test:

The weight of the fiber had changed from initially being 0.13 g to 30.13 g, indicating the absorption of liquid. The water retention percent was calculated using the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Water absorption (\%)} &= \\ &= \frac{\text{weight after immersion} - \text{weight before immersion}}{\text{weight before immersion}} \times 100\% \\ &= \frac{10.82\text{g} - 0.13\text{g}}{0.13\text{g}} \times 100\% \approx \mathbf{82.2\%}\end{aligned}$$

(Fig 10) Absorption test

Tensile strength test:

The product was hung from a stand using a thread. Weights were added one by one, and the pad was kept under stress to test its strength. This was compared with a disposable sanitary pad. The apparatus is as shown as in Fig 11.

Results of the tensile strength test:

Our product was able to withstand 140 g. Compared to the disposable, plastic pad, Pocea clearly ahead and did not tear when the first one did.

(Fig 11) Tensile strength test

Flammability test:

The extracted fiber was burnt and checked for ash residue formation as shown in Fig 12. To compare results a disposable sanitary pad was also burnt.

Flammability test results:

After burning the fiber, ashes were obtained (Fig 12). This indicated a successfully passing of this test. While, the disposable sanitary pads melted, confirming presence of plastic (Fig 13).

(Fig 12) Flammability test, burning the extracted fiber

(Fig 13) Flammability test, burning the disposable sanitary pad.

Biodegradability test:

The product was buried under soil for a few weeks to test whether it is biodegradable. It was left for 2 weeks with adequate moisture and sunlight to replicate outdoor conditions (Fig 14).

Biodegradability test results:

After time has passed, it was clear to see that the fibers were disintegrating and mixing with the soil, unlike its non-biodegradable counterpart.

(Fig 14) Biodegradability test

Leakage test:

20 ml of water was dropped onto the product surface. It was left on for a minute and checked afterwards for leakage on the underside.

Leakage test results:

Moisture was not observed at the bottom of the pad, resulting in a positive result.

(Fig 15) Leakage test

LAB RESEARCH RESULTS

(Zuzanna) Pocea fulfills all of the initial aims. It is safe, not susceptible to tearing and leakage (with absorbency of 82.2%). Additionally, the pad may be decomposed, contains no plastic and its production is not complicated and does not require any special equipment.

Therefore, Pocea pads have shown to be a good competitor against the disposable sanitary pads. In fact, we believe that it is an excellent, eco-friendly alternative to them.

The components of the pad that has been chosen are satisfactory and serve an important function in the final product.

The first layer of cotton cloth absorbs the liquid, where it seeps into the second layer of corn husk fiber. This layer absorbs the liquid with great efficiency. The beeswax and cinnamon layer show antimicrobial properties and prevent unabsorbed liquid (if any) from seeping into the garment. Beeswax wraps are water-resistant, preventing seepage. The final layer is another layer of cotton which acts as a final protective layer. Since the product is made from cotton cloth, which is porous and more breathable, it will be much more comfortable for the user to wear compared to the rough plastic woven fabric, which can cause rash and rubbing against the skin.

The results of the five tests (for absorption, tensile strength, flammability, biodegradability, and leakage) were satisfactory and were in favor of our product.

DISCUSSION

(Enosh) The Pocea Eco Pads have shown to be a good competitor against the disposable sanitary pads, and are an excellent alternative to them, showing their biodegradable properties considering the lab research results along with the literature review, we discussed about the problems of how the normal plastic based single used pads can be hazardous for both the environment as well as the human body. Pocea Eco Pads can be one of the best alternatives to this solution.

As discussed before there would not be any sort of plastic materials in the Pocea Eco Pads making it completely biofriendly. This will address the issue of how most single use plastic pads can end up in landfills and oceans as toxic waste. It is almost a call of nature to bring on a change to the system.

The waste product from retting, i.e., with further processing of the water can be used as a fertilizer for plants since it contains nutrients which help in the growth of crops.

As of cost it is meant to be a cost-effective product. In theory, the corn husk is mostly meant to be a waste material after the processing of corn. As the initial research was done in Kuwait the pricing or the cost of making will be in Kuwaiti dinar for comparison.

Cost of Corn Husk: 0 KD

Cost of Beeswax (per 100g): 2.5 KD (7.61 Euros)

Cost per 10g: 0.25 KD (0.76 Euros)

Cost of Cotton Cloth (per m): 0.5 KD (1.52 Euros)
Regular Pad Area (according to UNICEF): 22*10 cm²
From this 1m² cotton cloth, 4 pads can be stitched.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total cost} &= \text{Cost of cloth} + \text{Cost of corn husk} + \text{Cost of beeswax} \\ &= 0.5/4 + 0.1 \\ &= 0.225 \text{ KD (0.68 Euros)}\end{aligned}$$

When it comes to the EU provinces this price can be even cheaper due to the availability of the products.

CONCLUSION

(Enosh) This study concludes, that non-biodegradable disposable sanitary pads can be replaced by the more environmental-friendly Pocea Eco Pads. They can be a solution to both pollution as well as period poverty. They have shown the following properties: decomposable, reusable and affordable. Pocea Eco pads are an excellent alternative to disposable pads and will help in creating a change to a cleaner environment and will make hygiene and sanitation available to women all around the world, regardless of their income. "A pad for everyone". The motto of Pocea being the "The Nature's way to Nurture you".

As mentioned before following the 9 out of 17 United Nations Goals:

- No poverty
- Good Health and Well-Being
- Quality Education
- Gender Equality
- Clean water and Sanitation
- Responsible consumption, and production.
- Climate Action
- Life below Water
- Life on Land

Along with the introduction of Pocea we can encourage the legislative changes to help the EU achieve the "Sustainable Development Goals" 4,5 and 12. Doing so will accelerate the EU's efforts to achieve the "Sustainable Development Goals" (SDGs). By empowering mensurating community to lead independent lives, combating "menstrual poverty". We wish to contribute to gender equality considered to be *SDG goal 5*. Since "menstrual poverty" significantly hinders girls access to education, it also aids in achieving *SDG goal 4*, which is "Quality Education". Menstrual products made of reusable materials that are toxic-free help achieve *SDG goal 12*, which calls for a decrease in the use of single-use plastic products that contain harmful materials. Over here our innovation of corn husk fibers will be the main material for making most of these changes (Reusable & toxic-free menstrual products,

2018). Which means creating a much more sustainable product made with corn husk fibers, cotton cloth, cinnamon and beeswax that is more sustainable. Furthermore, making our product Pocea 100% ecofriendly is fulfilling the *SDG 14* and *15 (Life below water and life on land)* since Pocea uses non-plastic materials. The same reasons can contribute towards fulfilling the *SDG 13 (Climate Action)* as we discussed before, burning of plastics and micro-plastics can cause major harm to the organisms around. Finally last but not the least, we also satisfy the *SDG 1 (No Poverty)* where everyone is treated equally by providing proper, clean, high-quality and affordable sanitation. All thanks to our innovative product Pocea, which is indeed:

“The Nature’s Way to Nurture you”

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Ethics Form

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Ethics Application & Consent Form: Student Research

Anyone conducting research under the auspices of GISMA Business School, University of Applied Sciences (staff, students or visitors) where the research involves human participants or the use of data collected from human participants, is required to gain ethical approval before starting. This includes preliminary and pilot studies. Please answer all relevant questions in terms that can be understood by a lay person and note that your form may be returned if incomplete.

Before completing this form you will need to discuss your proposal fully with your supervisor(s).

Section 1: Project Details

- a) Project title: Pocea: Sustainable revolution in menstrual care
- b) Student name: Enosh Paul Niju, Zuzanna Katarzyna Kutowska
- c) Student Number: GH1026595, GH1026508
- d) Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Sara Ramzani
- e) Course category (tick one):
 - Masters
 - Bachelors
- f) Course/module title: Academic Writing and Research Methods (SS0324)
- g) Intended research start/end dates: 01.06.2024
- h) Intended research end date: 5.07.2024
- i) Country fieldwork will be conducted in: Kuwait

Section 2 - Research methods summary (tick all that apply)

- Interviews
- Focus Groups
- Questionnaires
- Action Research
- Observation
- Literature Review
- Controlled trial/other intervention study
- Use of personal records
- Secondary data analysis – **if secondary analysis used go to Section 4**
- Advisory/consultation/collaborative groups
- Other, give details: Lab research was conducted to develop a new product and then it's properties have been tested.

Please provide an overview of the project, focusing on your methodology. This should include some or all of the following: purpose of the research, aims, main research questions, research design, participants, sampling, data collection (including justifications for methods chosen and description of topics/questions to be asked), reporting and dissemination. Please focus on your methodology. *Minimum 100 words required.*

The purpose of this study is to conduct research regarding the development of a new innovative product: Pocea that is a sustainable alternative to conventional feminine menstrual pads. To do that, we have conducted a series of lab tests . These were a source of primary data for our inductive research. We have chosen to develop this product from scratch, meaning we needed to prepare all of the components of the pad ourselves and then testing its properties to ensure they meet our expectations. We have collected both qualitative and quantitative data (this data is only about the product components and is currently stored on private disks), that later were used to analyse the product further.

Section 3 – research Participants (tick all that apply)

a) Will your research involve human participants?

Yes

No

If No, go to section 4

b) Who are the participants for this project (i.e. what sorts of people will be involved)?

Tick all that apply

Early years/pre-school

Ages 5-11

Ages 12-16

Young people aged 17-18

Adults please specify below

Unknown – specify below

No participants

Because we do not have any participants, only lab research.

c) If participants are under the responsibility of others (such as parents, or medical staff) how do you intend to obtain permission to approach the participants to take part in the study? *(Please attach approach letters or details of permission procedures - see Section 8)*

NA

d) How will participants be recruited (identified and approached)?

NA

e) Describe the process you will use to inform participants about what you are doing

NA

f) How will you obtain the consent of participants? Will this be written? How will it be made clear to participants that they may withdraw consent to participate at any time?

NA

g) **Studies involving questionnaires:** please confirm that participants will be given the option of omitting questions they do not wish to answer?

Yes

No

***If no**, please explain why: NA

h) **Studies involving observation:** please confirm whether participants will be asked for their informed consent to be observed

Yes

No*

***If no**, please explain why: NA

i) Might participants experience anxiety, discomfort, or embarrassment as a result of your study?

Yes*

No

***If yes**, what steps will you take to explain and minimise this? NA

j) Will you debrief participants at the end of their participation (i.e. give them a brief explanation of the study)?

Yes

No*

***If no**, please explain why: Because we do not have any participants, only lab research.

k) Will participants be given information about the findings of your study? (This could be a brief summary of your findings in general; it is not the same as an individual debriefing)

Yes

No*

If no, why not? Because we do not have any participants, only lab research.

Section 4 - Secondary data analysis (only complete if applicable)

a. Are the data in the public domain?

Yes No

If no, do you have the owner's permission/license?

Yes No*

b. Will you be conducting analysis within the remit it was originally collected for?

Yes No*

c. **If no**, was consent gained from participants for subsequent/future analysis?

Yes No*

d. **If no**, was data collected prior to ethics approval process?

Yes No*

** Give further details in **Section 6 Ethical Issues***

*If secondary analysis is only method used **and** no answers with asterisks are ticked, go to **Section 8 Attachments**.*

Section 5 – Data storage and security

a) Please confirm that all personal data will be stored and processed in compliance with the General Data Protection Registration (GDPR).

Yes **No personal data has been collected.**

b) Will personal data be processed or be sent outside of the European Economic Area (EEA)?

Yes*

No

***If yes**, please confirm that there are adequate levels of protections in compliance with Data Protection Legislation and state what these arrangements are: **NA**

- c) Who will have access to the data and personal information, including advisory/consultation groups, and during transcription? **NA**

During the research

- d) Where will the data be stored? **Data was stored on a private disk.**

After the research

- e) Where will the data be stored? **Data is stored on a private disk.**

- f) How long will the data and records be kept for, and in what format? **Data will be stored on a private disk with no time restrictions.**

- g) Will the data be archived for use by other researchers?

Yes*

No

***If yes**, please provide details: **Data will be kept for future research since we (Zuzanna Katarzyna Kutowska, Enosh Paul Niju) are planning to continue our research on this topic.**

Section 6 – Ethical Issues

Are there particular features of the proposed work which may raise ethical concerns or add to the complexity of ethical decision making? If so, please outline how you will deal with these below.

It is important that you demonstrate your awareness of potential risks or harm that may arise as a result of your research. You should then demonstrate that you have considered ways to minimise the likelihood and impact of each potential harm that you have identified.

Ethical concerns may include, but not be limited to, the following areas:

- Methods
- Sampling

- Recruitment
- Informed consent
- Potentially vulnerable participants
- Sensitive topics
- Risks to participants and/or researchers
- Confidentiality/Anonymity
- Disclosures/limits to confidentiality
- Data storage and security both during and after the research
- Reporting
- Dissemination and use of findings

There are no ethical issues for our lab research as we collected no personal data.

Section 7 – Further information

Outline any other information you feel is relevant to this submission, using a separate sheet or attachments if necessary

We conducted lab research only and so there were no participants hence there were no personal data that was collected.

Section 8 – Attachments

Please attach the following items to this form, or explain if not attached:

- a) Information sheets and other materials to be used to inform potential participants about the research, including approach letters
Yes No N/A
- b) Consent form
Yes No N/A
- c) The proposal for the project
Yes No N/A
- d) Full risk assessment
Yes No N/A

Section 9 – Approval Process

All correspondence on your ethics approval should come through your supervisor.

If your study does not involve human participants or the use of data collected from human participants, your supervisor may grant you approval to conduct your research directly. This must take place in writing. Please note that your supervisor may consult with the University Ethics Sub-Committee (UESC) before granting you approval.

If your study involves human participants or the use of data collected from human participants, your supervisor will forward your application to the UESC. The UESC convenes once per month. For urgent cases, a Chair's action may be sought.

The UESC will review your project and then decide to approve it, reject it, or ask for revisions. Students cannot appeal the UESC' decision.

You may only begin data collection once you receive notification that your project has ethical approval. If the circumstances of your study change after approval, it is your responsibility to complete a further application.

Section 10 – Declaration

I have read, understood, and will abide by the preceding set of guidelines:

Yes No

I have discussed the ethics issues relating to my research with my supervisor

Yes No

I confirm that to the best of my knowledge:

The above information is correct and this is a full description of the ethics issues that may arise in the course of this project

Name: Enosh Paul Niju, Zuzanna Katarzyna Kutowska

Date: 04.07.2024.

Once complete, please submit your complete ethics forms to your supervisor